

Developing Robust and Generalizable AI for Diagnostic Support Across Medical Imaging Modalities

Ethan Dack

Univeristy of Bern
ethan.dack@unibe.ch

Abstract

Fueled by rapid advances in artificial intelligence (AI), data is increasingly becoming one of the most valuable resources in the world. However, AI is not a magical solution; poor-quality data leads to poor-quality outcomes, and without data altogether, it is impossible to build systems that can support humanity in critical areas such as disease diagnosis.

Throughout this PhD, our work has been grounded in solving problems with careful attention to the limited data at hand, contributing meaningfully to the ongoing transformation of 21st-century healthcare. We have addressed a diverse range of tasks across multiple medical imaging modalities, including:

- Applying vision-language pretraining methods to chest computed tomography (CT) scans and corresponding radiology reports for COVID-19 diagnosis.
- Curating a large-scale chest CT dataset to pretrain masked autoencoders (MAEs) aimed at improving diagnosis of interstitial lung diseases (ILDs).
- Performing segmentation and classification on ultrasound images.
- Investigating dataset bias in large, open-source X-ray datasets.

Our research explores various model architectures, leverages open-source models and datasets, and evaluates performance across numerous tasks. One of our key findings is that self-supervised learning holds great promise for the future of medical imaging. However, the importance of thoughtful and rigorous data curation remains paramount.

Main Research Report

0.1 Research Problem and Motivation

Initiated in the midst of the global COVID-19 research surge, this work began with a focus on developing computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems for lung disease detection. However, the scope quickly broadened to address a variety

Fig. 1: **Three medical imaging modalities are investigated.** We perform AI research on CT, X-ray and ultrasound.

of challenges across different medical imaging tasks. Faced with limited computational resources and a shortage of large, annotated datasets, we turned to self-supervised learning techniques, drawing on insights from the broader computer vision community to tackle the classical problems of data scarcity and lack of labels. As a data sample in Figure 1, our efforts have spanned multiple modalities and tasks, including disease diagnosis, image segmentation, and investigating dataset bias in large, open-source datasets. Collaborating closely with physicians, our overarching goal has been to develop models with real clinical relevance and to provide empirical insights into the capabilities and limitations of self-supervised approaches in data-constrained medical settings. Beyond clinical applicability, we are equally committed to ensuring that these models are robust and reliable. To that end, we have begun exploring the role of bias in medical imaging and its impact on the development and deployment of AI models.

0.2 Relevance and Related Work

When AI started to gain traction with regard to lung disease diagnosis, initial methods focused on supervised learning [5] [1] [6]. When the global pandemic started, this experience quickly transitioned into developing CAD tools for COVID-19 [13]. These workflows relied on human experts for the labelling, which is time-consuming and inefficient. Looking to newer self-supervised methods such as contrastive learning and masked model learning, we are able to make efficient use of data with the absence of labels [4] [32] [16] [8]. These methods are able to learn meaningful representations to be used in downstream tasks. Furthermore, AI methods have developed to encompass more than one modality for learning, which are still being expanded and investigated [24] [14]. These methods have been invaluable in addressing the scarcity of ILD data [9] by learning without labels and utilising COVID-19 imaging data to help learn useful features. We further expanded our work to the ultrasound modality for segmenting abdominal organs [15] with limited masks by fine-tuning foundation models [23], models that have also made use of large amounts of unlabelled data.

Fig. 2: **Self-supervised methods investigated.** We explore two popular pre-training methods, Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training (CLIP) and MAE pre-training, within this work. In (a), we can observe the pretraining method based on CLIP, and in (b), we can see the masked image modelling adapted for 3D medical volumes.

Recent works have begun to revisit the popular task of “Name That Dataset” in the non-medical domain. [22] [31] [27]. The investigation of large open-source chest X-ray datasets, which are often subjected to the creation of foundation models with the aforementioned self-supervised techniques, the same task has yet to be investigated on these popular datasets. We wish to investigate the root cause of dataset bias in these medical image datasets [10].

0.3 Scientific Approach

Self-supervised learning has been detrimental to the progress made in learning without annotations. Unsupervised learning had been well established, but understanding the representations had remained difficult. Self-supervised methods allow the models learned to harness their representations to be used in downstream tasks. In our initial project, we had access to a small cohort of chest CT scans with their respective radiological reports. This provided an opportunity to apply vision language pretraining, which has been previously investigated in non-medical imaging. The text and image modalities both have their own respective encoders to convert the data to a latent space of the same dimension. Between embeddings, we make use of the cosine similarity as a loss metric so future embeddings are more closely aligned. This work bootstrapped different models to find the best solution to working with a small amount of data. In the next area, we investigate the use of masked image modelling for 3D medical volumes. Influenced by natural language processing, this enables us to learn useful representations with the imaging modality alone. Thanks to the introduction of the Vision Transformer (ViT), dividing an image into patches has been well established. Following the pipeline in part (b) of 2, once the image has been patchified, the patches are passed through encoder blocks. A subset of patches

Fig. 3: **Ultrasound segmentation explored.** We have the original image on the left, ground truth in the middle and the fine-tuned MedSam prediction on the right.

is then randomly selected for masking and reconstruction, and the results are compared to the ground truth. These methods both learn representations to be used in downstream tasks such as disease diagnosis [7].

Ultrasound segmentation played a minor role in this PhD, but nonetheless was explored as shown in Figure 3 taken in [15]. This study investigates the use of a foundation segmentation model, SAMed [23], for abdominal ultrasound (US) imaging. SAMed [23] builds upon Segment Anything Model (SAM) [20], leveraging its powerful segmentation capabilities while being specifically adapted for medical imaging. To tailor it for semantic segmentation in the medical domain, several architectural modifications were introduced, improving its performance on specialised data.

Dataset bias has recently gained significant attention, though its exploration began in 2011 [27]. We replicate the experiments proposed in 2011, applying them to popular open-source medical imaging datasets of the same modality using a variety of modern neural networks. For four selected datasets, we task a model with identifying the originating dataset of a randomly chosen image. To give a visualisation, we created Figure 4. After training the models, we investigate how they perform this task with apparent ease. Through simple analysis, we aim to explain the mechanisms enabling models to accomplish this task effectively.

We make extensive use of existing deep learning architectures and foundation models in all projects to advance our research.

0.4 Proposed Solution

Our vision-language pretraining explores bootstrapping the best combination of text and vision encoders to be used for the downstream task, which is a multiclass zero-shot evaluation, diagnosing intricate details of the lung. At the time of our work, most pretrained models were only available for 2D images,

Fig. 4: **Dataset origin classification experiments.** We research dataset bias in popular large open-source chest X-ray datasets by evaluating how easy it is to predict the dataset origin.

and we had to take influence from Walsh et al. [28] for processing our 3D CT images. Using the lung mask model, we multiplied the lung mask by our original scan and then selected four random slices along the axial dimension to create an RGB montage. Contrastive learning is known to work best with larger batch sizes [4] [3], so this enabled us to increase the batch size compared to if we had tried to work with 3D images. Shown in part (a) of Figure 2, for training purposes, we base our forward pass on CLIP; we align the output embeddings of the respective encoders by calculating the logits of each modality and passing these into separate cross-entropy loss functions. We investigated varying the context length and whether more useful information was stored at the end of the report or the beginning. Different compared to previous works, for the zero-shot evaluation, we used word clouds to speculate the appropriate templates and create a list of positive-negative template pairs for a given class. Given a montage-text pair and a positive-negative template pair, we pass the montage into the vision encoder and the positive-negative prompts into the text encoder, multiply the text embeddings by the vision embedding, and pass these through a column-wise softmax to get our final multiclass predictions.

When conducting masked modelling research, we curated a large dataset of chest CT scans in the hope of improving disease diagnosis for lung disease, where data is traditionally scarce. Starting with 500 in-house scans, we increased this to over 5,000 with the help of scans taken throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. All scans are processed the same and resized to (128, 128, 128), and masked autoencoders are trained with ablations investigating the patch size and loss metrics. We replicate the experimental setup from [5] [12], solving one binary and one multiclass classification task. To fine-tune our MAE, we patchify each

volume and append a learnable class token ([CLS]) to the resulting tokens. Cross-entropy loss is used for both tasks. For the binary task, classes are roughly balanced (45:55), while the multiclass setting is more imbalanced. To address this, class weights are computed as $w_i = \frac{N}{n_i}$ and incorporated into the loss function.

In our ultrasound segmentation study, we collected 286 ultrasound images and corresponding masks from a local hospital to segment and classify abdominal organs and free fluid. To enhance the dataset size, we employed various data augmentation techniques. Since SAMed was initially trained on abdominal multi-organ Synapse CT scans, we fine-tuned its weights for ultrasound (US) imaging. This transfer learning approach improved the model’s ability to segment abdominal organs and free fluids. An example of the segmentation can be seen in Figure 3.

The dataset bias study, as far as we are aware, was the first experiment to perform the dataset origin experiments in the medical setting. Selecting the four commonly used X-ray datasets: MIMIC [19], CheXpert [18], NIH [29] and PadChest [2], we train 3 different neural networks on the task. To expand the work and also validate our findings, extensive transformations were performed on the datasets to understand in more detail how models can predict the dataset’s origin. The dataset transformations include cropped images and removed machine artefacts, semantic segmentations, contours and lung and heart only images. We randomly sample 100,000 frontal images from each dataset to ensure balance and resize all images to (512, 512), stored in the same data format. Patient data can only appear in train or test sets, not both. Once we trained our models, we visualised our models with the use of GradCams [25] [33] to understand how the model made a prediction. On top of this, we performed a semantic analysis to calculate percentages of semantic masks. Lastly, additional experiments were run with augmentations, patch shuffling, pixel shuffling and drastic image resizing.

0.5 Results and Contributions

Table 1: **Comparison of class-independent (CI) vs. class-dependent (CD) templates.** CheXzero uses ViT-B/32+GPT2; RN50 is ImageNet pre-trained; MedCLIP is a Swin transformer. RN50 and MedCLIP use RadBERT with context lengths 100 and 200, respectively. All models are fine-tuned on our dataset. HL: Hamming Loss, SubAcc: Subset Accuracy.

Model	Template	Macro-F1	Micro-F1	Precision	HL ↓	SubAcc ↑
CheXzero [26]	CI	0.55	0.62	0.60	0.47	0.05
	CD	0.71	0.74	0.72	0.29	0.23
RN50 [17]	CI	0.46	0.51	0.48	0.51	0.12
	CD	0.50	0.53	0.52	0.45	0.21
MedCLIP [30]	CI	0.57	0.60	0.58	0.44	0.13
	CD	0.58	0.62	0.61	0.42	0.15

One key highlight from our vision-language results stood out as particularly impactful. Unlike previous studies, our approach assigns a unique set of template pairs to each zero-shot class. This allows us to better align visual features with class-specific prompts. For instance, the positive prompt for pneumonia was often phrased as “consistent with” a formulation that would not be appropriate for a different condition, such as pulmonary embolism. As illustrated in Table 1, applying class-dependent prompts leads to substantial improvements across all three metrics, most notably, an 18% increase in subset accuracy. All prior baseline results were obtained using class-agnostic templates.

Table 2: **Binary vs. Multiclass classification results.** **Blue rows** indicate our method; **gray rows** are baseline comparisons. FT = full fine-tuning; LP = linear probing.

Binary Classification		
Method	F1 Score	Val Loss
MAE (FT)	0.69 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.29
MAE (LP)	0.71 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.06
Inception-ResNet [28]	0.71 ± 0.02	2.62 ± 1.07
ViT-B [28]	0.61 ± 0.06	2.44 ± 0.79
Radiomic Features [12]	0.70 ± 0.08	0.57 ± 0.07
Multiclass Classification		
Method	F1 Score	Val Loss
MAE (FT)	0.48 ± 0.07	1.78 ± 0.48
MAE (LP)	0.51 ± 0.05	1.45 ± 0.41
Inception-ResNet [28]	0.47 ± 0.05	5.63 ± 2.78
ViT-B [28]	0.33 ± 0.05	5.01 ± 1.02
Radiomic Features [12]	0.48 ± 0.09	1.23 ± 0.12

Secondly, our masked autoencoder results showed promising increases in the multitask task, and we note how difficult the task is due to the small dataset. The binary classification results in Table 2, MAE linear probe and Inception-ResNet perform best; radiomics shows low loss but high variance. In multiclass Table 2, the MAE linear probe leads with 0.51, outperforming fine-tuned MAE by 0.03. Fine-tuning caused faster overfitting. MAE variants consistently outperform Walsh et al. [28] in validation loss, though Fontanellaz et al. [12] achieves the lowest loss though with greater variability in F1.

The ultrasound task was also challenging due to the limited amount of data. As shown in Table 3, overall performance was modest, with an average Dice score of 0.43 and accuracy of 0.64 across all classes. The bladder achieved the highest Dice (0.63) and accuracy (0.77), while the pancreas was the most difficult, with the lowest Dice (0.11) and accuracy (0.35). Variability across organ classes highlights the difficulty of consistent segmentation in low-data ultrasound settings.

Table 3: Dice coefficient and accuracy results per class and averaged over all classes.

Class	Dice	Accuracy
Bladder	0.6271	0.7691
Gallbladder	0.4759	0.7256
Kidney	0.4907	0.6642
Liver	0.4924	0.6291
Pancreas	0.1115	0.3501
Spleen	0.3744	0.5581
Free fluid	0.4066	0.7695
All	0.4255	0.6380

Table 4: Average F1 scores by image type for each model.

Model	Cropped	Semantic	Contour	Lung & Heart
AlexNet [21]	97.82	85.49	86.27	95.46
ResNet50 [17]	99.28	86.59	88.62	98.96
ViT-B-16 [11]	95.43	68.37	61.31	91.64
Average	97.51	80.15	78.73	95.35

The most recent work in our dataset bias exploration showed fascinating results and emphasised how neural networks have such a deeper understanding of images when compared to humans. Modern models reached high accuracy in dataset classification, particularly on complex semantic and contour tasks. Surprisingly, contour-based models outperformed their semantic counterparts. CNNs consistently outperformed ViTs, especially on semantic and contour images, likely due to ViTs’ reliance on structural cues that are less apparent in these representations. In contrast to prior findings [31], anatomical structure had minimal influence on performance; instead, bias was largely driven by pixel intensity and texture. Slightly reduced performance on cropped and lung-heart (LH) images suggests ViTs may be less biased toward texture. Visualisations confirmed that models focused heavily on lung and heart regions, and even extensive augmentations had little effect on classification accuracy. Ablation studies further supported that shape information had a limited impact, reinforcing texture as the dominant factor driving model performance.

0.6 Open Challenges and Future Work

Data acquisition remained a persistent challenge across projects due to limited data availability, the rarity of certain diseases, and resource constraints faced by clinical partners. As computer vision and machine learning researchers, our focus should ideally be on working with imaging data rather than being directly involved in the data acquisition pipelines. However, the reality often requires close collaboration with clinical teams, which adds to the complexity of research work-

flows. Additionally, with the rapid growth of AI, models are becoming increasingly large, demanding significantly more GPU memory (VRAM). This trend is not sustainable for many research institutions. If it continues unchecked, only the most well-funded universities will be able to support cutting-edge experimentation. This highlights the urgent need for research focused on more computationally efficient models and training techniques. Another challenge—perhaps an obvious one—is working with 3D medical volumes. These images can be extremely large; some modern scanners produce volumes that are several gigabytes in size, exceeding the capabilities of current GPUs. This often necessitates down-sampling, which can compromise the quality or integrity of the data. There is also a need for better tools and practices around managing and organising large medical datasets. Open-source software solutions for efficient data storage and access would greatly benefit the research community. Finally, maintaining consistency in preprocessing and experimental pipelines is crucial. At present, many researchers use different methods, making reproducibility and validation difficult. One potential direction is to focus more on small-data problems, but such work is often criticised by reviewers for lacking the scale needed for clinical relevance.

References

1. Anthimopoulos, M., Christodoulidis, S., Ebner, L., Christe, A., Mougiakakou, S.: Lung pattern classification for interstitial lung diseases using a deep convolutional neural network. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* **35**(5), 1207–1216 (May 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2016.2535865>
2. Bustos, A.e.a.: Padchest: A large chest x-ray image dataset with multi-label annotated reports. *Medical Image Analysis* **66**, 101797 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2020.101797>
3. Chen, C., Zhang, J., Xu, Y., et al.: Why do we need large batchsizes in contrastive learning? a gradient-bias perspective (2022)
4. Chen, T., Kornblith, S., Norouzi, M., Hinton, G.: A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations (2020), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2002.05709>
5. Christe, A., Peters, A., Drakopoulos, e.a.: Computer-aided diagnosis of pulmonary fibrosis using deep learning and ct images. *Invest Radiol* (2019)
6. Christodoulidis, S., Anthimopoulos, M., Ebner, L., Christe, A., Mougiakakou, S.: Multisource transfer learning with convolutional neural networks for lung pattern analysis. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics* **21**(1), 76–84 (Jan 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JBHI.2016.2635662>
7. Dack, E., Brigato, L., Dedousis, V., et al.: Unmasking interstitial lung diseases: Leveraging masked autoencoders for diagnosis (2025), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.04429>
8. Dack, E., Brigato, L., McMurray, M., Fontanellaz, M., Frauenfelder, T., Hoppe, H., Exadaktylos, A., Geiser, T., Funke-Chambour, M., Christe, A., Ebner, L., Mougiakakou, S.: An empirical analysis for zero-shot multi-label classification on covid-19 ct scans and uncurated reports (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.01740>
9. Dack, E., Christe, A., Fontanellaz, M., et al.: Artificial intelligence and interstitial lung disease: Diagnosis and prognosis. *Investigative Radiology* **58**(8), 602–609 (Aug 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1097/RLI.0000000000000974>, epub 2023 Apr 11

10. Dack, E., Dai, C.: Understanding dataset bias in medical imaging: A case study on chest x-rays (2025), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.07722>
11. Dosovitskiy, A., Beyer, L., Kolesnikov, A., Weissenborn, D., Zhai, X., Unterthiner, T., Dehghani, M., Minderer, M., Heigold, G., Gelly, S., Uszkoreit, J., Houlsby, N.: An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. *ICLR* (2021)
12. Fontanellaz, M., Christe, A., Christodoulidis, e.a.: Computer-aided diagnosis system for lung fibrosis: from the effect of radiomic features and multi-layer-perceptron mixers to pre-clinical evaluation. *IEEE Access* (2024)
13. Fontanellaz, M., Ebner, L., Huber, A., Peters, A., Löbelenz, L., Hourscht, C., Klaus, J., Munz, J., Ruder, T., Drakopoulos, D., Sieron, D., Primetis, E., Heverhagen, J.T., Mougiakakou, S., Christe, A.: A deep-learning diagnostic support system for the detection of covid-19 using chest radiographs: A multireader validation study. *Investigative Radiology* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1097/RLI.0000000000000748>
14. Girdhar, R., El-Nouby, A., Liu, Z., Singh, M., Alwala, K.V., Joulin, A., Misra, I.: Imagebind: One embedding space to bind them all (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.05665>
15. Hamed, Z., Brigato, L., Dack, E., Schütz, M., Lehmann, B., Exadaktylos, A., Mougiakakou, S., Krummrey, G.: Ai-based analysis of abdominal ultrasound images to support medical diagnosis in emergency departments. *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* **325**, 16–21 (May 2025). <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI250209>
16. He, K., Chen, X., Xie, S., Li, Y., Dollár, P., Girshick, R.: Masked autoencoders are scalable vision learners (2021), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.06377>
17. He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., Sun, J.: Deep residual learning for image recognition (2015), <https://arxiv.org/abs/1512.03385>
18. Irvin, J.e.a.: Chexpert: A large chest radiograph dataset with uncertainty labels and expert comparison. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* (2019)
19. Johnson, A.E.W.e.a.: MIMIC-CXR: A De-identified Publicly Available Database of Chest Radiographs with Free-text Reports. *Scientific Data* **6**, 317 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0322-0>
20. Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., et al.: Segment anything. *arXiv:2304.02643* (2023)
21. Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., Hinton, G.E.: Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (2012)
22. Liu, Z., He, K.: A decade’s battle on dataset bias: Are we there yet? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.08632* (2024)
23. Ma, J., He, Y., Li, F., Han, L., You, C., Wang, B.: Segment anything in medical images. *Nature Communications* **15**, 654 (2024)
24. Radford, A., Kim, J.W., Hallacy, C., Ramesh, A., Goh, G., Agarwal, S., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Mishkin, P., Clark, J., Krueger, G., Sutskever, I.: Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision (2021), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>
25. Selvaraju, R.R., Cogswell, M., Das, A., Vedantam, R., Parikh, D., Batra, D.: Grad-cam: Visual explanations from deep networks via gradient-based localization. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*. pp. 618–626 (2017)
26. Tiu, E., Talius, E., Patel, P., Langlotz, C.P., Ng, A.Y., Rajpurkar, P.: Expert-level detection of pathologies from unannotated chest x-ray images via self-supervised learning (2020)

27. Torralba, A., Efros, A.A.: Unbiased look at dataset bias. In: CVPR 2011. pp. 1521–1528 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2011.5995347>
28. Walsh, S., Calandriello, L., Silva, M., Sverzellati, N.: Deep learning for classifying fibrotic lung disease on high-resolution computed tomography: a case-cohort study. *Lancet Respir Med* (2018)
29. Wang, X., Peng, Y., Lu, L., Lu, Z., Bagheri, M., Summers, R.M.: Chestx-ray8: Hospital-scale chest x-ray database and benchmarks on weakly-supervised classification and localization of common thorax diseases. In: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). pp. 3462–3471 (2017)
30. Wang, Z., Wu, Z., Agarwal, D., Sun, J.: Medclip: Contrastive learning from unpaired medical images and text (2022), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.10163>
31. Zeng, B., Yin, Y., Liu, Z.: Understanding bias in large-scale visual datasets. In: The Thirty-eighth Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (2024)
32. Zhang, Y., Jiang, H., Miura, Y., Manning, C.D., Langlotz, C.P.: Contrastive learning of medical visual representations from paired images and text (2022), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.00747>
33. Zhou, B., Khosla, A., Lapedriza, A., Oliva, A., Torralba, A.: Learning deep features for discriminative localization. In: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). pp. 2921–2929 (2016)